

REWET: RESTORING WETLANDS TO TACKLE CLIMATE CHANGE ISSUES

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WETLANDS CAN SUPPORT CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION

Wetlands provide important ecosystem services such as flood mitigation, water quality improvement, and groundwater aquifer recharge, all while maintaining biodiversity. Wetlands also play a critical role in sequestering carbon. Despite covering only 6% of the Earth's surface, wetlands alone hold 30% of all carbon stored on land, twice the amount stored in the world's forests. Intact wetlands sequester carbon from the atmosphere through plant photosynthesis and by acting as sediment traps for runoff. Carbon is held in the living vegetation as well as in litter, peats, organic soils, and sediments that have built up, in some instances, over thousands of years.

When wetlands are burned or drained for agriculture, however, they turn from a net carbon sink to a net carbon source. CO₂ emissions from peatland fires, drainage, and peat extraction are the equivalent of 10% of annual fossil fuel emissions. Keeping carbon locked away in wetlands ecosystems is absolutely critical to achieving global climate goals, yet wetlands have become a threatened ecosystem, with an estimated 64% of the world's wetlands lost since the 1900s due to urbanization – Europe alone has lost more than 55% of its wetlands in just one century. Moreover, the world's urban population is projected to increase to 68% by 2050 – a 13% increase since 2018 – requiring more land for housing and economic activities and further increasing stress on remaining wetland ecosystems. Not only is it fundamental to maintain existing wetlands, but it is also essential to restore degraded wetlands to reduce the effects of the extreme weather conditions we are increasingly experiencing. While there has been a large focus on assessing and understanding the restoration of coastal wetlands and the carbon they store, so-called “blue carbon,” clear guidelines are lacking for the restoration of freshwater wetlands, floodplains, and peatlands to maximize carbon uptake and minimize greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in a holistic manner that also benefits biodiversity and local communities.

WETLANDS RESTORATION AGAINST GHG: THE REWET PROJECT

REWET (REstoration of WETlands to minimize emissions

and maximize carbon uptake – a strategy for long-term climate mitigation) is an EU-funded project focusing on determining how the restoration and management of wetlands can be optimized to maximize carbon uptake in balance with natural processes and biodiversity conservation. REWET brings together 18 partners from nine countries (Spain, Austria, the Netherlands, Finland, Belgium, Estonia, Italy, Germany, and Portugal) representing universities, research and technology organizations, non-governmental organizations, public bodies, and small and medium enterprises. Partners are working together to develop REWET's methodology that will be applied to restore seven selected wetlands.

In REWET, we are adopting a holistic look at sustainable wetland restoration by identifying effective management strategies to conserve biodiversity, reduce GHG, and consider social and economic impacts, all while adapting these practices to prepare for future climate conditions. To achieve this, measuring and monitoring the biodiversity and ecosystem services produced by wetlands -while also simulating future needs and alterations in response to climate change caused by rising temperatures or drought -is crucial. Our work focuses on two areas: (1) the evidence-based restoration of seven degraded wetland sites, and (2) mapping wetlands across Europe.

The seven chosen wetlands for REWET are natural sites in different conditions with one thing in common: they all need to be restored to the natural trajectory they were on before humans intervened to exploit their fertile soils. We call these sites “Open Labs” (OLs) because they are open spaces in nature that can support research and serve as laboratories in “real life.” The restoration strategy for the selected OLs is based primarily on rewetting the sites, which means reintroducing water to the dried ecosystems. This is the primary restoration treatment of choice for wetlands because when rich carbon soils are dry, they emit large amounts of GHG and lead to a loss of biodiversity. We have also installed Eddy Covariance (EC) towers, providing GHG and meteorological data, in each of the OLs. The EC towers constantly measure the gas exchange between the land surface and the air, allowing REWET to assess conditions and adapt to implement the best practice.

In addition to the research on OLs, the mapping of wetlands in Europe will provide insights into EU member states' actions on wetlands by identifying countries that are currently restoring and conserving these habitats and recognizing those that urgently need to apply sustainable restoration practices to mitigate climate change. Based on the OLs and mapping outcomes, REWET partners will create models to estimate how wetlands in the EU can act as carbon sinks under various climate change scenarios while simultaneously preserving biodiversity and ecosystem services. This will involve analyzing wetlands' greenhouse gas emissions, carbon sequestration, and other factors. Finally, REWET will develop a replication roadmap and policy guidelines for sustainable wetlands restoration based on our findings.

TESTING RESTORATION METHODOLOGIES: REWET OPEN LABS

REWET restoration activities will follow an evidence-based methodology designed, implemented, and monitored in the seven OLs. These include freshwater wetlands, peatlands, and floodplains in the Netherlands, Austria, Finland, Estonia, Belgium, Italy and Portugal. REWET selected these sites based on their climatic and geographic conditions, type of wetland, vulnerability to natural disasters, the socio-cultural context and governance. As part of the project, we will define in detail the specific future climate scenarios for each OL to allow for the delivery of effective and fit-for-purpose restoration methodologies compatible with climate change trends at each site that both fully

recovers the wetland ecosystem, but in a manner that maximizes the potential of wetlands to act as carbon sinks. Partners will design restoration activities to allow replication in other wetlands, increasing the long-term impact of the REWET project. The monitoring system for the OLs includes not only the scientific aspects, such as the detailed measurement of greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O), soil and water chemistry, but also an analysis of biodiversity, ecosystem services, economic changes in the area, and the social impact in the local community.

OPEN LABS

OLI: The Netherlands - Peatland

Coordinated by the Wageningen Environmental Research Institute, the REWET OLI is located in the Weerribben-Wieden National Park, in the Overijssel province of the Netherlands. The national park covers more than 10,000 hectares and is considered to be the largest fen peatland in north-western Europe. The landscape has been formed

Photo credit: REWET

Open Lab Estonia

by centuries of human intervention, especially the excavation of peat and reed cutting. The parks' habitats are threatened by hydrological disturbances and water quality issues. Within the REWET project, we will assess the re-establishment of natural water levels, including periodic flooding, as well as study water level manipulation in combination with vegetation mowing to reduce wetland soil nutrient levels. The Weerribben-Wieden National Park will set an example of large-scale restoration which could stimulate biodiversity, improve greenhouse gas uptake and water quality, and increase the area's overall value.

OL2: Austria - Floodplain

The REWET OL2 is located at the Morava River, close to the border with Slovakia, and is coordinated by BOKU

Open Labs Localizations

University. The Morava floodplains are Austria's only near natural lowland river, and most of the ecological problems of the area are caused by the river regulation measures implemented from the 1930s to the 1980s: 36 meanders were cut off and 75% of the river banks stabilized on the river. The area was restored with an EU LIFE project between 2011 and 2019 when three main problems were addressed: lack of natural river sections with unpaved shores, lack of lateral connectivity (river-floodplain), lack of river islands and intact side arms. Within REWET, we will monitor GHG emissions, biodiversity (mainly flora), and land use change in the restored areas.

Open Lab Finland

OL3: Finland - Peatland

The University of Eastern Finland and the University of Oulu are coordinating REWET OL3. Ylpässuo is a small minerotrophic open mire in the northwest corner of Pohjois-Savo in Kiuruvesi, with several endangered plants and bird species. This peatland has been affected in the past decades by the edge draining due to forestry management actions that are typical across Finland and that disrupted the hydrological connection between the mire and the surrounding environment. In 2020, 11 of the 139 ha of the area were protected by the Natural Heritage Foundation. The site is now recovering from the drainage treatments. Within REWET, partners will restore the protected area to regain the original watery mire character, measure carbon fluxes, and investigate water quality.

OL4: Estonia - Peatland

REWET OL4 is located in Ess-soo, in southwest Estonia, and is coordinated by the University of Tartu. The peatland is of limnogenic origin, and most of the bog is part of the landscape protection area where the peat layer varies from 2 to 6 m. The eastern part of the bog was extensively drained for peat extraction and then abandoned in 1994.

The site has several sub-sites that are being treated with different restoration approaches, including: a control site, three sites with sphagnum cultivation under different water table depths, and one shallow water wetland that will be revegetated with common reed. Monitoring for the REWET project will include GHG emissions, water level increase, and the distribution of sphagnum mosses and other bog species.

OL5: Belgium - Upper Catchment Floodplain

In the Belgian Haute Ardennes region, OL5 comprises two sites coordinated by Wetlands International: Stream Bêche (with restoration activities) and Stream Emmels (with monitoring activities) in the Wallonia region. The Haute Ardennes were characterized by large areas of moors, which have almost completely disappeared following the widespread drainage of soils for spruce plantations. Partners will disconnect existing drainage channels in Stream Bêche, so that a much larger portion of the precipitation will start infiltrating the soil again. Stream Emmels has a beaver-created wetland and was restored in 2005 through a change of land use and the removal of drainage channels. REWET monitoring will include hydrological and biological factors, and GHG emissions. OL5 will help demonstrate the natural sponge concept in a region impacted by 2021 summer floods.

OL 6: Italy - Fluvial Wetland

OL6 research activities are coordinated by the Po River Basin Authority and the University of Parma. The oxbow lake (Lanca di Gussola) in the central part of the Po River Basin, in the province of Cremona, is part of the UNESCO Biosphere Reserve "Po Grande." A river meander and a secondary channel separated from the main channel by an embankment only intermittently connect with the Po River, preventing oxbow lake flooding and water renewal. Within REWET, partners will lower the embankment to increase the frequency of flooding at moderate Po discharge, producing cascading implications for water chemical qualities, ecosystem biodiversity, and ecosystem functioning, thus guaranteeing the environmental requalification of the oxbow lake. REWET will monitor GHG fluxes as a proxy for biogeochemical functioning, allowing exploration of the regulation of GHG emissions along multiple gradients.

OL 7: Portugal - Low peatland

Paúl da Gouxa in Portugal is the seventh REWET project Open Lab. This peatland is a natural reserve located in the municipality of Alpiarça, in the administrative region of Lezíria do Tejo, and it is coordinated by the University of Évora and the Municipality of Alpiarça. With an area

of about 140 ha, Paúl da Gouxa is a unique example of a wetland of inland waters, with a low peatland, swampy willow groves, and reeds in great condition. Before 2005, when the first restoration activities started on the site, the area was severely degraded as it was used as a peat extraction site and a dump. For the REWET project, partners will undertake floodplain restoration soil reprofiling and native plant propagation for revegetation to address the impacts of sand extraction practices. Moreover, REWET will assess the capability of peat bogs to generate economic gains contributing to the conservation of the land.

FUTURE PROSPECTS AND GLOBAL SCALABILITY: REWET CONTRIBUTIONS

To achieve a 55% net reduction in GHG emissions by 2030, in 2018 the European Commission implemented the LULUCF (land, land use change, and forestry) Regulation. It ensures that GHG emissions from land use and forestry – including wetlands by 2026 – are balanced by at least the equivalent removal of CO₂. But REWET goes further than this net zero approach. The REWET project will support the implementation of the LULUCF Regulation – as well as the Green Deal, the Nature Restoration Law, and the Soil Health Law – by testing clear and solid methodologies for data provision and analysis to show that wetland restoration activities can contribute to the EU's 2030 emission reduction target, while also benefiting biodiversity and human wellbeing. Another one of the project's objectives is to provide policy recommendations of best practices for wetland restoration through guidelines and workshops, and by compiling the lessons learned from REWET and other wetland restoration projects. REWET partners aim to contribute to major international frameworks (such as the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services - IPBES and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change - IPCC), substantiating effective policy options and supporting member states to comply with LULUCF. To promote and encourage the restoration of wetlands with scientific evidence and experimental data, by the end of the REWET project in 2026, an online platform will be available to support sustainable wetland management and restoration decisions. To analyze the impact of wetlands restoration activities, mathematical and computational models will be developed, taking into account variables like GHG emissions, carbon sequestration, economic losses/gains, and societal impacts over various time periods (2022-2030, 2030-2050, 2050-2100, 2100-2300). By including the social component, the model will be accessible to the average user who can

see the effects of restoration measures in their day-to-day lives, rather than just the indicators referring to the effects on the economy or environment. The results of the machine-learning analyses will be available with clear reports.

The REWET project is driven by climate objectives, but is designed to deliver holistic wetland restoration approaches that not only sequester carbon, but also initiate native recovery, improve biodiversity and ecological integrity, create sustainable livelihood opportunities, and otherwise improve human wellbeing.

REFERENCES

- Cherry, J.A. (2011) Ecology of Wetland Ecosystems: Water, Substrate, and Life. [Nature Education Knowledge 3\(10\):16](#). Retrieved 20/06/2023.
- Ramsar (2018) [Wetlands: why should I care?](#). Retrieved 20/06/2023.
- Minnesota Board of Water and Soil resources (2019). [Carbon sequestration in wetlands](#) | Retrieved 20/06/2023.
- Ramsar (2018) [Wetlands: essential for a sustainable urban future](#). Retrieved 20/06/2023.
- Zedler, Joy B., Kercher, S. (2005) «WETLAND RESOURCES: Status, Trends, Ecosystem Services, and Restorability». [Annual Review of Environment and Resources, vol. 30, fasc. 1](#), November 2005, pp. 39–74. .
- [68% of the world population projected to live in urban areas by 2050](#), says UN | UN DESA | United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. Retrieved 26/07/2023.
- European Commission (2018). [Regulation \(Eu\) 2018/841](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on the inclusion of greenhouse gas emissions and removals from land use, land use change and forestry in the 2030 climate and energy framework.
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